

An Analysis of Students' Anxiety in Speaking English at First Grade of SMK Nasional

Julian Chandra^{1*}, M. Saleh Yahya Himni²

¹STKIP YDB Lubuk Alung, Indonesia

Institut Studi Islam Sunan Doe, Indonesia

*Corresponding Email: julienandra447@gmail.com, yhimni191@gmail.com

Article Info

Received: 20-03-2023

Accepted: 27-03-2024

Published: 30-04-2024

Abstract

The objective of this study was to identify the factors contributing to students' nervousness when speaking English and to assess their English speaking proficiency at SMK Nasional 2 Kayu Tanam. This research employs qualitative methodologies with a descriptive orientation. Two instruments were utilized in this research, specifically the LFCAS questionnaire developed by Horwitz in 1986 and the speaking test created by Brown in 2004. The research sample comprised 35 students, divided across two classes: class X accounting and class X TSM 2. The sample was obtained using purposive sampling. The research data was gathered through the administration of a questionnaire and a speaking test in two classes: class X accounting and class X TSM 2 SMK Nasional 2 Kayu Tanam. The results of the LFCAS questionnaire indicated that communication apprehension was at 33.5%, fear of negative evaluation at 24.56%, and test anxiety at 41.94%. The outcomes of the class X accounting and X TSM 2 in the five aspects are as follows: vocabulary 19.93%, grammar 19.26%, fluency 19.77%, pronunciation 20.6%, and understanding 20.44%. Based on the LFCAS questionnaire, pupils can be classified as either low or below average, whereas the results of the students' speaking test are classified as excellent.

Keywords: Anxiety, Speaking Ability, SMK Nasional 2 Kayu Tanam

How to Cite: Chandra, J., & Himni, M., S., Y. (2024). An Analysis of Students' Anxiety in Speaking English at First Grade of SMK Nasional. *Asshika: Journal of English Language Teaching & Learning*. Page, 1-9. Vol. 1, Number 2, 2024.

Introduction

Language has an important role for human life (Fanni et al., 2023). Language can be used as our everyday interactions (Dai, 2023). People will express their ideas, emotion, and desire by using language (Tunca et al., 2023), and one of them is English. English is a second or foreign language that is learned by people all over the world, one can communicate with other people from different countries by using English. English is an international language that must be mastered by people from various countries in the world to communicate with each other (Himmatova, 2023).

English learning that are taught in school contain four skills that must be mastered by students, namely listening, reading, writing and speaking (Yaqin & Yasir, 2024). The main point in learning English is how we can communicate using that language, in

communication speaking is an important skill that must be mastered because in oral communication there are several elements that must be understood such as grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, fluency and understanding.

When students express their knowledge of their various feeling to others they must speak clearly, fluently and accurately so that others can understood what they mean. This mean that students need the ability to be good at speaking, one of the psychological factors related to student's reluctance to speak is that students feel anxious about speaking the foreign language they are learning, it can be a problem for them or maybe they will fail in their skills.

Based on the experience of researcher finding problems with signs of anxiety among students. First, the researcher found that many of the students became agitated creating avoidance and reducing participation in class. They are afraid and embarrassed to practice English especially in speaking, because they are worried they will make mistakes they think if they make mistakes the teacher will get angry and their friends will mock and laugh at them, so they prefer to be silent and sit passively.

Secondly, some of them believe that English is a difficult subject, such belief can affect their self-confidence and make them feel worried in class. Finally, when they were asked to speak they started to get anxious and some of them couldn't produce sound or intonation even after several repetitions because they felt unsure they could practice their English. In other words, anxiety can hinder students from achieving their English learning goals.

Speaking in English is one of the basic competencies that must be understood and mastered, especially in the current era (Nugraha et al., 2024). Speaking is the use of language to communicate with other people, namely activities that involve two or more people whose participants are listeners and speakers (Khairani, 2023). Speaking ability is the student's ability to express ideas orally which is presented with a speaking score (Miranda & Wahyudin, 2023). The ability to speak is very important in mastering English because students who learn English are required to master speaking ability in order to be able to communicate well with each other.

Speaking ability refers to the capacity to effectively articulate sounds and express thoughts, ideas, and emotions (Amir et al., 2023), to others with confidence, naturalness, honesty, accuracy, and responsibility. It involves overcoming psychological barriers such as shyness, low self-esteem, tension, and speech impediments. When speaking, students not

only need to recall the language, but also pay attention to the intonation. However, the sense of anxiousness can sometimes lead to a lack of confidence or blunders in their speech. Anxiety is extensively documented in the field of psychology (Bantjes et al., 2023). Anxiety typically originates from the human body as a natural response to specific circumstances (Bourban, 2023). Anxiety is typically characterized by a sense of threat, unease, tension, or apprehension (Wang et al., 2023). The objective of this study was to identify the factors contributing to students' nervousness when speaking English and to assess their English speaking proficiency at SMK Nasional 2. Planting Wood. This research employs qualitative methodologies utilizing a descriptive framework. Two instruments were utilized in this research, specifically the LFCAS questionnaire developed by Horwitz in 1986 in (Estep et al., 2023) and the speaking test created by Brown in 2004 in (Nair et al., 2023). The research sample comprised 35 students from two classes, specifically class X accounting and class X TSM 2. The sample was obtained using purposive sampling. The research findings were obtained through the administration of a questionnaire and a speaking exam in two specific classes, namely class X accounting and class X TSM 2 SMK Nasional 2x11 Kayu Tanam. The details of the results are as follows: The LFCAS questionnaire yielded the following results: communication apprehension at 33.5%, fear of unfavorable evaluation at 24.56%, and exam anxiety at 41.94%. The results of the class X accounting and X TSM 2 courses are as follows: vocabulary score is 19.93%, grammar score is 19.26%, fluency score is 19.77%, pronunciation score is 20.6%, and comprehension score is 20.44%. Based on the LFCAS questionnaire, pupils might be classified as low or below, however the results of the students' speaking test are classified as very good.

Student's anxiety can occur at any time, for example students experience anxiety when asked to come to the front of the class, anxiety when speaking in public and so on. This anxiety often occurs with the ups and down of student academic achievement. There are two factors that can influence student learning achievement, namely factors from within the individual (internal) which include the physical condition and mental state of students and factors from outside the individual (external) which include environmental factors. One example of external factors is when students adapt to the school environment, related to school schedules such as assignments, which are dense and are felt for the first time after being at school. While examples of internal factors that influence student learning achievement are personality variables such as anxiety disorders (Liu et al., 2023).

Then, based on the explanation above, the writer wants to conducted a research entitles “An Analysis of Students’ Anxiety in Speaking English at First Grade of SMK Nasional 2 Kayu Tanam”.

Research Method

This research is qualitative with descriptive approach. Arikunto (2019) in (Indahsari et al., 2023) states that descriptive research is research that is intended to investigate the circumstances, conditions or other things that have been mentioned, the results of which are presented in the form of a research report. Sugiyono (2018) in (Nurwulan & Maulida, 2023) descriptive research is a study conducted to determine independent variables without comparing or connecting with other variables. This means that this study only wants to know how the state of the variable itself is without any influence or relationship to other variables such as experimental research or correlation.

The purpose of this research was to find out the factors what caused students anxiety and to find out the extent to which students ability to speaking English in class X SMK Nasional 2x11 Kayu Tanam.

Population

Population is a generalization area that consist of subjects or objects that have certain quantities and characteristics (Rivaldo & Nabella, 2023). Whereas the small group that is observed is called the sample and the large group that is generalized is called the population. The population in this research were students of class X SMK Nasional 2x11 Kayu Tanam which consisted of three classes, this table show the population of the first grade of SMK Nasional Kayu Tanam as follows:

The population of students at first grade

No	Class	Students
1	TSM 1	22
2	TSM 2	21
3	Accountancy	18
Total		61

Sample

Sample is very important in conducting because the data obtained from the sample (Douglas et al., 2023). In this research the researcher used a purposive sampling is the process of selecting samples by taking subjects that are not based on the regional level, but are taken based on a specific purpose (Martawijaya et al., 2023). This means that this research used purposive sampling where this research aims to determine student's anxiety in speaking ability in English lessons in class X SMK Nasional 2xII Kayu Tanam. So 2 classes were taken as samples consisting of 21 male students in the TSM 2 class and 18 female accounting classes, so that the total sample in this research was 39 students.

Instruments

The instrument is a tool to collect data or information (Manfredini et al., 2024). In this research the researcher used two instruments, namely questionnaire and students speaking tests to obtain data on student's anxiety and speaking ability.

In this research, the researcher used a questionnaire from the foreign language classroom anxiety scale (LFCAS) developed by Horwitz et al (1986) in (Estep et al., 2023) which was used to obtain information about foreign language anxiety. LFCAS covers three aspects namely communication apprehension, fear of negative evaluation and test anxiety, the questionnaire was not made by the researcher directly but was adapted from Horwitz et al (1986) directly on the grounds that this questionnaire is more valid and reliable without making researching the questionnaire to obtain its validity and reliability.

Questionnaire LFCAS

No	Aspects	Number of Items	Total
1	Communication Apprehension	1, 4, 9, 14, 15, 18, 24, 27, 29, 30, 32	11
2	Fear of Negative Evaluation	2, 7, 13, 19, 22, 23, 31, 33	8
3	Test Anxiety	3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 16, 17, 20, 21, 25, 26, 28	14
Total			33

The results of this test considered as data on students speaking abilities, to assess students speaking ability the researcher was used Brown (2004) in (Manfredo et al.,

2023)theory whereas the assessment consists of five elements, namely vocabulary, grammar, fluency, pronunciation and comprehension.

Validity and Reliability

Horwitz (1986) reported the reliability measure of the LFCAS interval showed an alpha coefficient of 0,93 the eight week retest reliability showed $r=83$ ($p<0,001$) and the predictive validity coefficient for the final score was 49 ($p<0,03$, $n=35$) in the two classes initial Spanish -54 ($p=0,01$, $n=31$) in two early French classes, an example of another study by Aida (1994) if it shows an internal reliability of 0,94 the reliability of the LFCAS version internal was calculated by Cronbach alpha coefficient. The result showed that the internal reliability of the instruments ranged between 89 and 91 this means that the items in this instrument have high internal reliability.

Content validity refers to the nature of the content included in the instrument and the specifications that the research used to formulate the content (Navarro-Pérez et al., 2023). Content validity is very important because it is a very accurate measure of what it is supposed to measure, for this reason the researcher asked supervisors and English teachers to assess whether the items used in the speaking test were appropriate or not.

Technique of Data Collecting

The first step the research distributed questionnaire to 39 students to find out their anxiety in learning English, before students filled out the questionnaire the research first explained the questionnaire items and how to fill them out so that students could understand and fill them properly and correctly provide a checklist for each question item. The second step is to conduct a speaking test to students to find out the extent to which students are able to speaking English.

Technique of Data Analysis

In analyzing research data researcher used Linkert scale with 5 point from (Sugiyono, 2013) to calculate the data from the questionnaire and speaking test. Ranging from strongly agree (SA) to strongly disagree (SD), the scale used ranged from 5-1 where strongly agree was given a score of 5 and strongly disagree was given a score 1.

Linkert Scale

Category	Score
Strongly Agree	5
Agree	4
Neutral	3
Disagree	2
Strongly Disagree	1

Sources: Sugiyono (2013)

To calculate the amount of data from the questionnaire and speaking test used the formula from Arikunto (2013).

$$P = \frac{F}{N} \times 100\%$$

P = percentage

F = frequency of students' scores in questionnaire and speaking test based on indicator

N = students score max based on indicator

Result and Discussion

LFCAS questionnaire

Figure 1

Based on the graph above, it can be seen as a whole the result of the LFCAS questionnaire used in class X accounting and X TSM 2. Based on the communication apprehension obtained a result of 33,5%, fear of negative evaluation obtained a result of 24,56% and test anxiety obtained a result of 41,94%. This means that from the two classes it can be concluded that the students English speaking ability based on the LFCAS questionnaire is categorized as low or below.

Figure 2

Based on the graph above it can be seen as a whole the result of the speaking test that has been carried out by researcher in class X accounting and X TSM 2, of the five elements there are Vocabulary obtained a result of 19,93 %, Grammar obtained a result of 19,26 %, Fluency obtained a result of 19,77 %, Pronunciation obtained a result of 20,6 % and Comprehension obtained a result of 20,44 %. So that it can be concluded from the students speaking test in English which is categorized as very good.

Conclusion

Based on data analysis and research findings, the researcher used the LFCAS questionnaire which was adapted from Horwitz 1986 which consisted of 33 questions and for the speaking test the researcher adapted from Brown 2004 which contains the five elements used in the speaking test namely vocabulary, grammar, fluency, pronunciation and comprehension.

Can be seen from the results of the questionnaire and speaking test class X accounting and X TSM 2, the results of the LFCAS questionnaire and the researcher speaking test it can be concluded as follows, based on the LFCAS questionnaire communication apprehension obtained a result of 33,5 %, fear of negative evaluation obtained a result of 24,56 % and test anxiety obtained a result of 41,94%. This means that from the two classes it can be concluded that the students English speaking ability based on the LFCAS questionnaire is categorized as low or below.

Based on the speaking test class X accounting and X TSM of the five elements there are Vocabulary obtained a result of 19,93 %, Grammar obtained a result of 19,26 %, Fluency obtained a result of 19,77 %, Pronunciation obtained a result of 20,6 % and Comprehension obtained a result of 20,44 %. So that it can be concluded from the students speaking test in English which is categorized as very good.

References

- Amir, R. A., Korompot, C. A., & Baa, S. (2023). A Study on the Effectiveness of Using Digital Material of Podcast to Improve Student's Speaking Ability. *Journal of Excellence in English Language Education*, 2(2), 189–198.
- Bantjes, J., Hunt, X., & Stein, D. J. (2023). Anxious, depressed, and suicidal: Crisis narratives in university student mental health and the need for a balanced approach to student wellness. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 4859.
- Bourban, M. (2023). Eco-Anxiety and the Responses of Ecological Citizenship and Mindfulness. In *The Palgrave Handbook of Environmental Politics and Theory* (pp. 65–88). Springer.
- Dai, D. W. (2023). What do second language speakers really need for real-world interaction? A needs analysis of L2 Chinese interactional competence. *Language Teaching Research*, 13621688221144836.
- Douglas, B. D., Ewell, P. J., & Brauer, M. (2023). Data quality in online human-subjects research: Comparisons between MTurk, Prolific, Cloud Research, Qualtrics, and SONA. *Plos One*, 18(3), e0279720.
- Estep, J. A., Sun, L. O., & Riccomagno, M. M. (2023). A luciferase fragment complementation assay to detect focal adhesion kinase (FAK) signaling events. *Heliyon*, 9(4).
- Fanni, S. C., Febi, M., Aghakhanyan, G., & Neri, E. (2023). Natural language processing. In *Introduction to Artificial Intelligence* (pp. 87–99). Springer.
- Himmatova, N. N. (2023). Psychological Aspects of Learning a Foreign Language. *Spanish Journal of Innovation and Integrity*, 13, 1–6.
- Indahsari, H. K., Suyanta, S., Yusri, H., Khaerunnisa, N., & Astuti, S. R. D. (2023). Analysis of the Use of Android-Based Edusan Learning Media on Students' ICT Literacy Skills. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, 9(5), 2312–2318.
- Khairani, A. (2023). An Analysis of Speaking Performance Between Higher and Non-Higher Achievers: A Case Study at Department of English Education of UIN Suska Riau. *Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau*.
- Liu, X.-Q., Guo, Y.-X., & Xu, Y. (2023). Risk factors and digital interventions for anxiety disorders in college students: Stakeholder perspectives. *World Journal of Clinical Cases*, 11(7), 1442.
- Manfredini, D., Ahlberg, J., Aarab, G., Bender, S., Bracci, A., Cistulli, P. A., Conti, P. C., De Leeuw, R., Durham, J., & Emodi-Perlman, A. (2024). Standardised tool for the assessment of bruxism. *Journal of Oral Rehabilitation*, 51(1), 29–58.
- Manfredo, M. J., Vaske, J. J., Bruyere, B. L., Field, D. R., & Brown, P. J. (2023). Society and natural resources: A summary of knowledge.
- Martawijaya, M. A., Rahmadhanningsih, S., Swandi, A., Hasyim, M., & Sujiono, E. H. (2023). The Effect of Applying the Ethno-STEM-Project-based Learning Model on Students' Higher-order Thinking Skill and Misconception of Physics Topics Related to Lake Tempe, Indonesia. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 12(1), 1–13.
- Miranda, J. A., & Wahyudin, A. Y. (2023). Pre-Service Teachers' Strategies in Improving Students' Speaking Skills. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 4(1), 40–47.
- Nair, V. K., Farah, W., & Cushing, I. (2023). A critical analysis of standardized testing in speech and language therapy. *Language, Speech, and Hearing Services in Schools*, 54(3), 781–793.
- Navarro-Pérez, J.-J., Samper, P., Sancho, P., Georgieva, S., Carbonell, Á., & Mestre, M.-V. (2023). Development and content validation of a comprehensive tool for assessing risk and protective factors in children and adolescents: The ACRAM. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 145, 106761.
- Nugraha, I. M. I. P., Rahman, A., & Sotlikova, R. (2024). Investigating EFL Police Officers' Learning Needs and Problems in English Listening and Speaking Skills: An English Specific Purposes (ESP) Context. *Journal of Language and Literature Studies*, 4(1), 84–97.
- Nurwulan, L. L., & Maulida, H. (2023). How Do Remote Audit and Client Company Size Affect Audit Fees? *JRAK*, 15(1), 108–113.
- Rivaldo, Y., & Nabella, S. D. (2023). Employee performance: Education, training, experience and work discipline. *Calitatea*, 24(193), 182–188.
- Tunca, S., Sezen, B., & Wilk, V. (2023). An exploratory content and sentiment analysis of the guardian metaverse articles using leximancer and natural language processing. *Journal of Big Data*, 10(1), 82.
- Wang, X., Li, Y., Khasraghi, H. J., & Trumbach, C. (2023). The mediating role of security anxiety in internet threat avoidance behavior. *Computers & Security*, 134, 103429.
- Yaqin, A. H., & Yasir, D. (2024). The English learning effort: Optimizing English speaking skills through total physical response method for fourth grade elementary school at Kuala Lumpur of Indonesian school (SIKL). *International Journal of Contemporary Sciences (IJCS)*, 1(5), 153–172.